

did not adversely affect germination; nor were they phytotoxic.

Seed soaking and foliar spraying were superior to sprouted-seed soaking treatments in suppressing GM at 25 DAS. In some treatments, this trend persisted up to 35 DAS. □

Influence of some weather factors on rice stem borer (SB) infestation

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Deadheart/whitehead (DH/WH) incidence was recorded weekly during 1988-89 at the Rice Research Station, Tirur. Mean weather parameters 14 d before the observation date [maximum temperature (°C) (X_1), minimum temperature (°C) (X_2), relative morning humidity (%) (X_3), and rainfall (mm) (X_4)] were correlated with DHWH incidence.

The fitted multiple regressions to predict DH and WH damage were $Y = 1.2754 + 0.0913 X_1 - 0.04843 X_2 + 0.1067 X_3 + 0.2934 X_4$ and $Y = 13.9020 - 0.0336 X_1 - 0.0933 X_2 - 0.0980 X_3 - 0.0318 X_4$, respectively. The regression equations explained approximately 50% variation in DH/WH damage due to weather, but none of the factors significantly contributed to SB infestation. Instead, continuous cropping allows the pest to multiply. □

Chemical control of gall midge (GM) in the rice nursery

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) damage causes seedlings to break while being pulled for transplanting. Populations also build up in the nursery to attack the transplanted crop.

We studied the effect of soaking seeds in seven insecticides (0.1%) and of two granular insecticides on GM incidence in the nursery during the 1987 wet season.

We soaked Tikkana (NLR27999) seed in insecticidal solutions for 12 h, then incubated it for 36 h. Water-soaked seed was used in granular treatments and as a control.

Nursery plots of 1 × 1 m were laid out in a randomized complete block design with 17 treatments, replicated three times.

Granular and foliar insecticides were applied (see table). We randomly pulled 200 seedlings per treatment at 25 and 40 DAS to assess GM incidence.

Differences in GM incidence at 25 and 40 DAS among treatments were significant. Incidence at 25 and 40 DAS was lowest in chlorpyrifos seed-soaking treatments. The other insecticides, used for soaking seed alone or in combination with foliar spraying at 25 DAS, did not protect rice from GM for 25 d.

We confirmed that chlorpyrifos seed soaking (0.1 %) combined with foliar spraying at 25 DAS controls GM for 40 d in the nursery. □

Incidence of GM in nursery at Agricultural Research Station, Nellore, India.

Treatment	Incidence ^a (%)	
	25 DAS	40 DAS
1 Soil application of phorate 10 G at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 10 DAS	24.1 (29.3)	19.3 (25.8)
2 Soil application of carbosulfuron 3G at 1.25 kg ai/ha, 10 DAS	43.6 (41.3)	61.2 (51.5)
3 Seed soaking in monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.1%	52.0 (46.6)	64.2 (53.4)
4 T3 + foliar spray of monocrotophos at 0.05%, 25 DAS	48.5 (44.1)	64.6 (53.6)
5 Seed soaking in chlorpyrifos 20 EC at 0.1%	14.9 (22.6)	17.5 (24.0)
6 T5 + foliar spray of chlorpyrifos at 0.05%, 25 DAS	19.7 (24.8)	11.9 (20.0)
7 Seed soaking in phosphamidon 85 EC at 0.1%	53.2 (47.0)	55.9 (48.3)
8 T7 + foliar spray with phosphamidon at 0.05%, 25 DAS	46.0 (42.6)	68.2 (55.8)
9 Seed soaking in quinalphos 25 EC at 0.1%	27.9 (31.5)	33.5 (35.0)
10 T9 + foliar spray of quinalphos at 0.05%, 2.5 DAS	28.1 (32.1)	43.4 (41.2)
11 Seed soaking in methyl parathion 50 EC at 0.1%	59.4 (50.9)	63.7 (53.3)
12 T11 + foliar spray of methyl parathion at 0.05%, 25 DAS	42.3 (40.5)	54.0 (47.3)
13 Seed soaking in formothion 25 EC at 0.1%	48.8 (44.2)	55.1 (47.9)
14 T13 + foliar spray of formothion at 0.05%, 25 DAS	50.7 (45.4)	62.8 (52.8)
15 Seed soaking in demeton-S-methyl 25 EC at 0.1%	61.1 (51.5)	58.4 (49.8)
16 T15 + foliar spray of demeton-S-methyl at 0.05%, 25 DAS	60.7 (51.6)	65.7 (54.3)
17 Untreated control	55.5 (48.2)	61.2 (51.5)
LSD (P = 0.05)	12.30	10.28
CV (%)	18.09	13.71

^a Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values.

Mirid predation on brown planthopper (BPH) eggs

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We observed *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* predation on BPH eggs in an untreated IR1917-3-17 field during the 1987-88 dry season.

TN1 plants with BPH eggs were exposed in the field.

Field predation by *C. lividipennis* in untreated IR1917-3-17 at different cropping periods. IRR, 1987-88 dry season.

Days after transplanting	BPH eggs exposed ^a (no.)	Field predation by <i>Cyrtorhinus</i> (% ± SE)	<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> population per hill ^b (± SE)
35			0.25 ± 0.05
42			0.27 ± 0.04
49	329.9	3.85 ± 0.98	0.29 ± 0.05
56			0.42 ± 0.06
63	443.3	4.89 ± 0.77	0.63 ± 0.09
70			0.92 ± 0.11
77	562.3	8.06 ± 0.94	1.15 ± 0.12
84			0.82 ± 0.14
91	366.5	17.71 ± 2.57	1.25 ± 0.14
98			0.55 ± 0.08

^aAv of 30 replications. ^bCollected by FARMCOP machine. SE = standard error at 95% probability.